

Manuscript author	Year	Country/ Territory	Genetic cohort	Self-reported ethnicity	Age	N	Study Design	Recruitment method	Genetic ancestry	Asthma Definition
Studies of self-identified African Americans										
Flores et al.	2012	USA	REACH	African-American	Adult	329	Case-control	Emergency department	African	Physician-diagnosed asthma and asthma questionnaire
Flores et al.	2012	USA	BASS	African-American	Adult	467	Case-control	Community-based (clinical and non-clinical) convenience sampling	African	Self-reported physician-diagnosed asthma and medication use for asthma symptoms.
Vergara et al.	2013	USA	BASS+ GRAAD*	African-American	Ped and Adult	1382	Case-Control	GRAAD: Universities BASS: clinics and community	African, European	GRAAD: Self-reported asthma and a documented history of physician-diagnosed asthma (past or current)
Vergara et al.	2013	USA	REACH	African-American	Adult	378	Case Control	Emergency department	African, European	Physician-diagnosed asthma and asthma questionnaire
Studies of self-identified Hispanic Americans										
Choudhry et al.	2006	USA (Puerto Rico)	GALA I	Hispanic- American (Puerto Rican)	Ped and Adult	271	Case-Control	Primary care clinics	African, European, Native American	Physician-diagnosed and two or more symptoms in previous 2 years (wheeze, coughing, shortness of breath)
Pino-Yanes,	2015	USA, Mexico	CHS/ GALA I/ GALA II*	Hispanic- American (Puerto Rican, Mexican American, and Other Latino)	Ped and Adult	5493	Case-control/ cohort	GALA II: Community, clinics CHS: Schools	African, European, Native-American	GALA II: Physician diagnosis and report of symptoms and medication use within the past 2 years. CHS: Parental-reported physician-diagnosis
Salam et al.	2015	USA	CHS	Hispanic-American	Ped	1719	Cohort	Schools	African, Native-American, Asian	Parental-reported physician-diagnosis

Author	Year	Country/Territory	Cohort	Self-reported ethnicity	Age	N	Study Design	Recruitment method	Genetic ancestry	Asthma Definition
Kumar et al.	2012	USA	BBC	Multi-ethnic	Ped	1034	Cohort	Birth cohort	African, European	Three episodes of medically-attended wheeze in lifetime, evidenced by electronic medical record
Pino-Yanes et al.	2012	Canary Islands	-	-	Ped and Adult	734	Case-Control	Cases: hospitals, controls: blood bank	North- African, Iberian	Physician-diagnosed and fulfilled GINA guidelines
Vergara et al.	2013	Barbados	-	-	Ped and Adult	467	Family study	Families of probands from emergency department or clinics	African, European,	Self-reported asthma and documented physician-diagnosed asthma plus a history of wheezing without an upper respiratory infection or two out of four hallmark symptoms (wheezing with a URI, cough without a URI, shortness of breath, chest tightness)
Vergara et al.	2013	Jamaica	-	-	Adult	706	Case control	Birth cohort	African, European	ISAAC questionnaire(1) and a history of physician-diagnosed asthma
Vergara et al.	2013	Brazil	-	-	Ped	260	Ecological study	Random population sample	African, European	ISAAC questionnaire (1)
Da Silva et al.	2019	Brazil	SCAALA	-	Ped	1190	Cohort	Community	African	ISAAC questionnaire (1)
Vergara et al.	2013	Colombia	-	-	Ped and Adult	1133	Case Control	Clinic and outpatient centres	African, European	Standardized questionnaire in patients with a history of physician-diagnosed asthma
Akenroye et al.	2021	Peru	GASP	-	Ped and adult	727	Case Control	Random population sample	European, Native-American	Self-reported physician diagnosis of asthma and asthma symptoms or taking asthma medications within the past year

GRAAD - Genomic Research on Asthma in the African Diaspora; REACH - Reducing Emergency Asthma Care in Harlem; BASS - Baltimore Asthma Severity Study; GALA - Genes-Environment and Admixture in Latino Americans; CHS - Children's Health Study; Paed – paediatric; GINA - Global Initiative for Asthma, URI – upper respiratory tract infection, ISAAC - International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood; SCAALA - Social Change in Asthma and Allergies in Latin America. GASP - Genetic Asthma Susceptibility to Indoor Pollution in Peru study

**effect estimates are reported for all genetic cohorts combined, as the study did not provide individual effect estimates for each cohort.*

Table 1. Characteristics of eligible studies

eReferences

- e1. Salam MT, Avoundjian T, Knight WM, Gilliland FD. Genetic Ancestry and Asthma and Rhinitis Occurrence in Hispanic Children: Findings from the Southern California Children's Health Study. *PLOS ONE*. 2015;10(8):e0135384.
- e2. Pino-Yanes M, Thakur N, Gignoux CR, et al. Genetic ancestry influences asthma susceptibility and lung function among Latinos. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*. 2015;135(1):228-35.
- e3. Akenroye AT, Brunetti T, Romero K, et al. Genome-wide association study of asthma, total IgE, and lung function in a cohort of Peruvian children. *The Journal of allergy and clinical immunology*. 2021;148(6):1493-504.
- e4. Flores C, Ma S-F, Pino-Yanes M, et al. African ancestry is associated with asthma risk in African Americans. *PloS one*. 2012;7(1):e26807.
- e5. Vergara C, Murray T, Rafaels N, et al. African Ancestry is a Risk Factor for Asthma and High Total IgE Levels in African Admixed Populations. *Genetic Epidemiology*. 2013;37(4):393-401.
- e6. Choudhry S, Burchard EG, Borrell LN, et al. Ancestry-environment interactions and asthma risk among Puerto Ricans. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*. 2006;174(10):1088-93.
- e7. da Silva TM, Fiaccone RL, Kehdy FSG, et al. African biogeographical ancestry, atopic and non-atopic asthma and atopy: A study in Latin American children. *Pediatric pulmonology*. 2019;54(2):125-32.
- e8. Kumar R, Tsai HJ, Hong X, et al. African ancestry, early life exposures, and respiratory morbidity in early childhood. *Clinical & Experimental Allergy*. 2012;42(2):265-74.
- e9. Pino-Yanes M, Corrales A, Cumplido J, et al. No association between genetic ancestry and susceptibility to asthma or atopy in Canary Islanders. *Immunogenetics*. 2012;64(9):705-11.

Genetic Ancestry	Reference population (geographic region)	AIMs*	Method for estimating individual genetic ancestry	Study
African (N=6)	West Africa	95 AIMs	STRUCTURE	Flores et al. 2012
	Yoruba (Ibadan, Nigeria), HapMap II	144 AIMs 20 669 SNPs 237 AIMs	STRUCTURE ADMIXTURE STRUCTURE	Kumar et al. 2012 Pino-Yanes et al. 2015 Vergara et al. 2013
	Senegal, Cameroon, Ghana, Botswana	233 AIMs	STRUCTURE	Salam et al. 2015
	Not specified	44 AIMs	STRUCTURE	Choudhry et al. 2006
	Luhya (Webuye, Kenya),	370 539 SNPs	ADMIXTURE	Da Silva et al. 2019
Asian (N=1)	Cantonese (China)	233 AIMs	STRUCTURE	Salam et al. 2015
European (N=3)	Northern and Western European-descent Americans (Utah, USA), HapMap II	144 AIMs 20 669 SNPs 237 AIMs 107 095 SNPs	STRUCTURE ADMIXTURE STRUCTURE ADMIXTURE	Kumar et al. 2012 Pino-Yanes et al. 2015 Vergara et al. 2013 Akenroye et al. 2021
Iberian (N=1)	Mozabite Algerians and French Basques (HGDP)	83 AIMs	STRUCTURE	Pino-Yanes et al. 2012.
Native American (N=2)	Zapotec, Mixtec and Mixed (Oaxaca, Mexico)	233 AIMs	STRUCTURE	Salam et al. 2015
	Native American – not further specified	20 699 SNPs	ADMIXTURE	Pino-Yanes et al. 2015
	Bolivian Aymara, Maya, Mixtec, Nahuatl, Peruvian Quechua and Tlapanec	107 095 SNPs	ADMIXTURE	Akenroye et al. 2021

HGDP - Human Genome Diversity Project; AIMs – Ancestry Informative Markers; SNPs – single nucleotide polymorphisms

*numbers reflect total AIMs used across all genetic ancestries in the relevant study

Table S1. Reference populations used to determine genetic ancestry.

		Selection				Comparability	Case Control: Exposure Cohort: Outcome			Total
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4 [#]	Q1 [§]	Q1	Q2	Q3	
Flores et al. 2012 (REACH)	Response	a	a	b	a		a	a	a	
	Score	1	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	7
Flores et al. 2012 (BASS)	Response	b	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	0	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	6
Kumar et al. 2011	Response	a	a	a	a		c	a	a	
	Score	1	1	1	1	N/A	0	1	1	6
Pino-Yanes et al. 2014 (GALA I)	Response	a	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	1	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	7
Pino-Yanes et al. 2014 (GALA II)	Response	a	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	1	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	7
Pino-Yanes et al. 2014 (CHS)	Response	b	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	0	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	6
Salam et al. 2015	Response	b	a	a	a		a	a	c	
	Score	0	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	0	5
Choudhry et al. 2006	Response	a	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	1	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	7
Vergara et al. 2013 (Barbados)	Response	b	a	b	a		a	a	a	
	Score	0	1	0	1	N/A	1	1	1	5
Vergara et al. 2013 (Jamaica)	Response	a [^]	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	1	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	7
Vergara et al. 2013 (Brazil)	Response	a [^]	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	1	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	7
Vergara et al. 2013 (Colombia)	Response	b	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	0	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	6
Vergara et al. 2013 (USA - REACH)	Response	a	a	b	a		a	a	a	
	Score	1	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	7
Vergara et al. 2013 (USA - GRAAD/BASS)	Response	b	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	0	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	6
Pino-Yanes et al. 2012	Response	a	a	b	a		a	a	a	
	Score	1	1	0	1	N/A	1	1	1	6
Da Silva et al. 2019	Response	a [^]	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	1	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	7
Akenroye et al. 2021	Response	b	a	a	a		a	a	a	
	Score	0	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	6

[^]Where cases were defined using ISAAC questionnaire, a validated method of identifying asthma cases based on symptoms, this was awarded as 'A'

[#] This question is about causality (ensures that the outcome does not precede exposure). Since genetic ancestry is present at birth, it always precedes asthma. All studies awarded 'A'

[§] We do not believe that there are any confounders of the relationship between genetic ancestry and asthma, as there are unlikely any conventional co-variates (eg age, sex etc) that could cause genetic ancestry. See discussion. All studies awarded N/A (not applicable)

Table S2. Bias Assessment